

PROSPECTS OF USING PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT METHODS IN THE PUBLIC CIVIL SERVICE

Ismoilov Sardorbek Odiljonovich

Chief inspector of the Andijan regional branch of the Agency for the Development of Public Service under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Abstract: This article discusses the methods implemented in the field of performance management evaluation, the analysis of approaches in evaluating the efficiency, as well as the opinions of scientists from different countries and suggestions on using evaluation methods of senior civil service performance management in Uzbekistan based on the learned experience.

Key words: public civil service, performance management evaluation, executives, Management by objectives, 360-degree feedback, key performance indicators.

Forehead

Traditional methods such as classical attestation that originated in the Soviet era no longer meet the requirements of today. In order to succeed in the modern world, organizations in the public civil service need innovative management tools and methods focused on setting goals and determining the responsibilities of employees. Hence, application of performance management methods helps to motivate staff for new achievements and creative self-improvement.

Public civil service means a type of public service that is a professionally paid activity of citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan to ensure the exercise of the powers of state bodies in positions of public civil service.

Even though, in 2004, Harvard Business Review published the results of a study conducted to identify high-performing employees and determine the best incentive methods. More than a thousand managers and employees of companies took part in the study. According to the results of the study, on average, in each

company 5% of employees consistently work at a high level of efficiency, another 5-7% of employees consistently demonstrate unsatisfactory performance, and the remaining 88-90% of employees are required to correctly and effectively fulfill their goals and objectives, mandatory control is required. ¹ This, in turn, indicates that managers face challenges such as motivating employees, getting them interested in their work, and directing organizations towards strategic goals.

So that, market economy companies have developed a system based on the effectiveness of managers, and the use of advanced management practices that ensure efficiency and effectiveness at the level of public administration is proposed by representatives of the NPM (New Public Management) school of modern management.²

In the same way, Managerial performance assessment is defined as a formal and effective procedure for measuring work performance and results based on the manager's job responsibilities. The evaluation aims to determine how well the manager performs his or her duties. In this regard, modern methods such as “360 degrees”, “management by objectives” and “KPI” are used to assess the effectiveness of management personnel in countries around the world.

Therefore, as studies have shown, assessing the effectiveness of management activities of management personnel is one of the most important issues of our time. In this case, it is advisable to study the possibilities of using modern methods for assessing the effectiveness of management activities by management personnel, develop proposals, and establish their effective use.

In this article, we will consider in detail methods for assessing the effectiveness of the management activities of managers.

Management by objectives (MBO)

¹ Клочков А. В. KPI и мотивация персонала. Полный сборник практических инструментов. М.: Юрайт, 2011. 132 б.

² Osborne, D. Reinventing Government. How the Entrepreneurial Spirit is Transforming the Public Sector / D. Osborne, T. Gaebler. N.Y., 1992. 420 p

The method of Management by objectives was proposed by Peter Drucker in 1954 and later became very popular. Through the application of the method, the personal achievements of each employee were assessed, with emphasis placed on the results of the employee's work performed over a certain period of time, usually a year. In 1970s, the method was considered a universal way of assessing and motivating personnel.

The method is a systematic and organized approach that allows managers to focus on goals and achieve the best results. The essence of management by objectives is that the system of official goals at each level of company management is supplemented by the individualized, personalized goals of employees.

What I mean is, it can be concluded that the management by objectives method through assessment, corrects formation of the family tree of the organization's goals and provides the opportunity for implementation. Everyone who has their own goals will have an executor.

360 degree feedback

A 360-degree assessment is a method of gathering feedback that enables clients, managers, peers, direct reports and others to evaluate an employee's skills. This feedback is also compared to the employee's self-evaluation, giving a 360-degree look at one's performance. These assessments have been used for several decades in business coaching and leadership development, often with organizations developing their own 360 tools to meet specific needs and objectives. It is required from assessors to evaluate professional and performance qualities.

To be exact, 360-degree appraisal is successfully used in civil service of 9 OECD countries, such as Australia, France and South Korea.³ Based on the results of the research, it is 360-degrees the evaluation method is used to evaluate the performance of the executive employee and is carried out through external parties.

³ OECD (2019), OECD Survey on Strategic Human Resource Management (SHRM) [Электрон манба]: <https://doi.org/10.1787/888934032624>

Of course, in this process the assessee is required to give more importance to the process of corporate governance.

Key Performance Indicators (KPI)

An important role in systematizing the rational assessment of personnel performance was played by the work of Peter Drucker, who turned management into a scientific discipline. The concept of Management by Objectives which involves the process of agreeing on goals within the company between management and staff directly states that their goals are an assessment of the degree to which they have been achieved through key performance indicators, the term was first used in 1954.⁴

But finally, the performance indicators were formed only in 1992. In this year, professor Robert Kaplan of Harvard Business school and American businessman David Norton developed a system of setting and achieving goals in a company -called the System of Balanced Scorecard (BSC). KPI is a complex approached method on achieving goals through strategic management that is based on BSC.⁵

Currently, a KPI-based evaluation and incentive system is a methodology that has been developed for assessing the performance of employees and creating mechanisms for their appropriate incentives.

Key performance indicators (KPIs) have been used in the West for over 40 years, in CIS countries and in Russian for over 15 years. KPI is considered not only as a concept but also the basis of the companies' work and is accepted as a national idea in most developed countries like South Korea, Singapore, Hong Kong, Japan, Malaysia, Germany and the US.

Based on the analysis, the following proposals are recommended for evaluating the effectiveness of the management activities in the civil service in Uzbekistan:

⁴ Drucker, Peter F., "The Practice of Management", 1954. ISBN 0-06-011095

⁵ R.S. Kaplan, D.P. Norton. Using the Balanced Scorecard as a Strategic Management System // Harvard Business Review, 1996

1. Establishing the use of the "360 degrees" method in the evaluation of managers' professional and performance qualities;
2. To improve the efficiency and effectiveness of employees, it is necessary to approach their needs through a collective determination of their level of potential. It is necessary to gradually strengthen the weakest aspects of the management team's potential. It is advisable to use modern short-term training seminars;
3. It is necessary to reduce the additional tasks identified as the most negative factor in the performance of managers by evaluating them based on KPIs. This, in turn, helps to determine what tasks managers should focus on in order to achieve the organization's strategic goals.

Reference:

1. Law of the republic of Uzbekistan — On public civil service, 08.08.2022 й., National legislative information database, 09.08.2022 й., 03/22/788/0723-edition.
2. Ключков А. В. КPI и мотивация персонала. Полный сборник практических инструментов. М.: Юрайт, 2011. p 132
3. Osborne, D. Reinventing Government. How the Entrepreneurial Spirit is Transforming the Public Sector / D. Osborne, T. Gaebler. N.Y., 1992. p 420
4. OECD (2019), OECD Survey on Strategic Human Resource Management (SHRM) [Электрон манба]: <https://doi.org/10.1787/888934032624>
5. Drucker, Peter F., "The Practice of Management", 1954. ISBN 0-06-011095
6. R.S. Kaplan, D.P. Norton. Using the Balanced Scorecard as a Strategic Management System // Harvard Business Review, 1996